

TOF SIMS IMAGING FRACTOGRAPHY OF FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Scanning time-of-flight secondary ion mass spectrometry (ToF SIMS)), a highly surface sensitive microscopy, provided evidence of molecularly thin resin and/or contaminant layers in CFRP fracture surfaces. An inverse correlation between the intensity of fibre specific ions and surface treatment is demonstrated. For GRP, the presence of a silane rich interphase is identified.

1. INTRODUCTION

The application of conventional electron microscopy in the examination of composite fracture surfaces is well known and is a useful technique for revealing the morphology of such fractures. Where, however, very thin adhered resin overlayers are present on the surfaces of fibres, their detection requires the use of a technique which can identify the contrasting chemical compositions of the fibre and resin components in the material. Hence in previous work, the authors developed the application of secondary ion mass spectrometry, scanning SIMS, using an instrument fitted with a quadrupole detector, to produce microchemical maps of composite fractures at resolutions of $\leq 1 \mu\text{m}$, because of the presence of $7 \mu\text{m}$ diameter fibres in the composites (1). More recently, a highly sensitive SIMS system has become available which uses a time-of-flight (ToF) mass spectrometer, and in investigations of the interfacial properties in carbon and glass fibre composites, this type of SIMS has been used to analyse the surfaces of these fibres following adhesion promoting treatments (2,3). It was shown for example, that ToF SIMS spectra of silane coated glass fibres could reveal the complex molecular structure of the coating, from which secondary ions with masses up to 697 amu were detected. In this paper, we report the application of the ToF SIMS in imaging mode, for the characterisation of the fracture surfaces of epoxy resin matrix composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Carbon Fibres

A set of composite interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) test specimens were provided by Prof G Dorey, Materials and Structures Division, DRA, Farnborough, which had been fabricated with Type XA fibres and Shell Epikote 828 epoxy resin (a Diglycidyl ether of Bisphenol A - DGEBA resin).

Figure 1: Negative ion ToF SIMS spectra of carbon fibre-epoxy composite fractures containing (a) untreated (unoxidised) fibres, (b) surface treated (oxidised) fibres

Figure 4: Reciprocal of the normalised peak intensity of the fibre specific ions against degree of carbon fibre surface treatment (DFT) for a series of composite fracture surfaces.

The fibres had received a range of electrolytic surface treatments (DFT) and the details, together with the ILSS values, measured at the DRA, are given in Table 1. Transverse fracture surface from these test specimens were mounted for SIMS analysis.

Table 1: The interlaminar shear strengths (ILSS) of composites containing carbon fibres of varying surface treatment (DFT)

DFT/Cm ⁻²	ILSS/MPa
0*	77
25	82
230	93

*The 0 Cm⁻² fibre had still passed through the treatment rig, but at zero current between the fibres and the electrolyte.

2.2 Glass Fibres

Unidirectional specimens were prepared from E-glass fibres coated with (NH₂(CH₂)₃Si(OC₂H₅)₃) and Epikote 828 epoxy resin and then fractured for imaging SIMS analysis in order to probe the interfacial chemistry, within the composite. Results from previous analyses of the coated fibres formed the background information for the selection of specific secondary ions (4).

2.3 ToF SIMS Analysis

The specimens were mounted beneath a 1mm² grid holder and transferred into the vacuum chamber of a VGIX23S ToF SIMS system operating at a base pressure of $\leq 10^{-9}$ m bar. This was interfaced to a PDP11/53 data system operating with VGX7000T software for the acquisition and processing of spectra and images. The samples were excited with a pulsed, microfocussed 30KeV Ga⁺ ion beam and the secondary ions were extracted by the application of a bias voltage of + or -5kV to the sample, for the detection of positive or negative ions, respectively. Analyses were obtained from areas ($< 0.28\text{mm}^2$) beneath the centres of 1mm² holes in the grid, and one of the important roles of the conducting grid is to facilitate charge compensation with a low energy pulsed electron flood gun. This is an important aspect in SIMS analysis of specimens containing insulating components such as epoxy resin and glass. The analysis depth is only 1-2nm since the total ion dose is constrained to be in the "static" regime of less than 10¹³ ions cm⁻² of sample.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fracture Surfaces of Carbon Fibre Composites

An example negative ToF SIMS spectrum of an untreated fibre fracture surface is given in Fig 1a, with a number of the principal peak assignments. The peak at 69 amu has been assigned to CF₃⁻, because of the presence of the F⁻ peak at 19 amu. The significance attached to the detection of these two ions will be considered below. The ions at 24, 25 and 26 amu, C₂⁻, C₂H⁻ and CN⁻ are emitted strongly by the fibres, but not by the resin areas, whereas the ions at 16 and 17, O⁻ and OH⁻ are emitted by both components. The corresponding spectrum from a sample containing highly oxidised fibres, Fig 1b, has many similarities with the first. However, it is particularly interesting to note that the relative intensity of the peaks assigned to fibre specific ions at 24-6 amu is reduced in the second case. In the scanning mode, up to four ion images can be acquired simultaneously

Figure 2: $(O + OH)^-$ red/(24-6 amu) green overlay image from a composite fracture surface containing untreated carbon fibres (DFT = 0 Cm^{-2}). (Note: The original colour images are produced in monochrome.

Figure 3: $(O + OH)^-$ red/(24-6 amu) green overlay from a composite fracture surface containing oxidised carbon fibres (DFT = 25 Cm^{-2})

Figure 5: F^- (red)/(24-6 amu) green overlay from a composite fabricated from untreated carbon fibres (DFT = 0 Cm^{-2})

from a specified group of ions. A typical set for the analysis of this type of sample is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Ion images acquired during SIMS of carbon fibre composites

Image No	Mass Range amu	Ions Detected
1	0-400	all -ve ions
2	15.5-17.5	O ⁻ and OH ⁻
3	23.5-27.5	C ₂ ⁻ , C ₂ H ⁻ and CN ⁻
4	18.5-19.5	F ⁻

Subsequent image processing and overlaying using primary colours yields the location of the resin and fibre components in the fracture. Fig 2 contains an overlay image of the (O⁻ + OH⁻) (16-17 amu) red/(24-6 amu) green maps from an untreated fibre sample, and the filaments lie almost horizontal in this case. The fibres are clearly defined and the majority appear yellow or green due to emission of the 24-6 amu ions from the areas of fibre which have no resin overlayers attached even of nanometer thickness. Hence the failure in this case has been initiated at the relatively weak interface present between the untreated fibres and the epoxy matrix. In the corresponding overlay image for the sample containing highly oxidised filaments (Fig 3), the majority of the fibres are covered with a relatively thick resin layer and only a small fraction (on the right-hand side of the image) appeared yellow, where interfacial failure had occurred. The fact that only a minority of the fibres are free of resin, in contrast to the unoxidised fibres (Fig 2), is reflected in the relatively low intensity to the ion peaks at 24-26 amu in the spectrum in Fig 1b which is the average analysis over the whole area of the corresponding image. A number of SIMS analyses were conducted on this type of sample, covering the fibre surface treatment range, and in Fig 4, the relative intensity of the fibre specific peaks, normalised to the total ion intensity across the 10-50 amu range, NPI, vs DFT shows a distinct trend in which the proportion of clean fibre within the fracture surfaces decreases at higher treatment levels. This can be correlated with a corresponding improvement in the interfacial properties of the material as illustrated by the ILSS values in Table 1.

An organic fluorine compound was detected on the fracture surface and in Fig 5, an overlay of the F⁻ (19 amu) map, red/(24-6 amu) green shows that this is detectable on the surfaces of the exposed fibres, and is particulate in nature. The fibres actually passed over PTFE rollers in the electrolytic treatment rig and it is presumed that the reactive and adsorptive filaments picked up contaminant particles of PTFE during this process. Such contamination is potentially detrimental to adhesive bonding and this is another factor that should be borne in mind when considering all the aspects that could affect interface formation, including fibre surface functionality, microporosity and chemisorptive properties, as has been discussed previously by the authors (5). More specifically, the detection of various contaminants including siloxanes and phthalates, by ToF SIMS was reported in earlier work (2) on carbon fibres, which had received various surface oxidative treatments.

3.2 Fracture Surfaces of Glass Fibre Composites

A preliminary spectral study of the interaction of hydrolysed γ -aminopropyltriethoxysilane (HAPS) with glass surfaces reported elsewhere, was used to select fibre and resin specific ions for imaging the fracture surfaces (3,4,6).

Figure 6: CH^- (red)/ O^- (green) overlay from a silanised glass fibre-epoxy resin fracture surface

Figure 7: Si^+ (red)/ Ca^+ (green) overlay corresponding to Figure 6.

Negative ion images

The negative ion images of an overlay of CH^- (13 amu - green) and O^- (16 amu - red) sputtered from the fracture surface of the silanised fibre composite are presented in Figure 6. As has been discussed elsewhere (6) individual silanised glass fibres, after treatment with Diglycidyl ether of Bisphenol S (DGEBS) in hot toluene solution, are uniformly coated with a thin film of epoxy resin. However, on the molecular scale substrate aluminium sites incorporated into the siloxane layer may not be involved (4,6). Analogously, the silanised fibre surface, in this case, is entirely covered by the DGEBA epoxy resin. Thus, most of the intensity of the CH^- ion is given by the DGEBA resin matrix. The O^- ion can arise from all of the three main components; glass fibres, the HAPS deposit and the DGEBA matrix when it is sputtered from the fracture surface, but it is only given by the glass fibre surface when it emanates from the end of a broken fibre. From these arguments, this image demonstrates that the outer surface of each of the HAPS-coupled fibers in the composite is completely covered by the DGEBA resin as indicated by a uniform yellow colour present on the resolved single fibre surface and the good differentiation between the matrix and the broken fibre ends, which appear red in the overlay.

Positive ion images

Figure 7 shows an overlay of Si^+ (28 amu - red) and Ca^+ (40 amu - green) ions sputtered from the same fracture surface as Fig 6. Using a similar argument to that given above it follows that Si^+ can emanate from the glass fibres and/or the HAPS deposit. For the broken fibre ends it can only arise from the glass but for the fibre surface it can arise from the HAPS deposit. On the other hand Ca^+ can only arise from the glass. Thus the fractured glass fibres ends appear yellow as a result of the sputtering of Ca^+ and Si^+ . The presence of the HAPS deposit on the fibre surface is indicated by the uniform but weak red colour of the silanised fibre surface. From a comparison of the +ve and -ve ion images in Figs 6 and 7, it is apparent that the resin coating on the fibres is rich in siloxane. Therefore the presence of interfacial mixing of the HAPS deposit and the DGEBA resin in the interphase region of the composite is indicated.

Polished composite cross-section

To investigate the interphase region further images of a polished cross-section were created and the overlay image from CH^- and O^- ion maps is given in Fig 8. On the basis of the intense yellow halo around the glass fibres the presence of an interphase region of thickness $\sim 1.3 \mu\text{m}$ between the glass fibre and resin matrix in the composite is indicated. This is in agreement with the observations of Thomason (7). The secondary ion intensity from the resin areas is very low because of the highly crosslinked nature of the matrix. Therefore it appears that the interphase region has a lower crosslink density as a result of interpenetration of the epoxy resin and the siloxane adhesion promoter during fabrication of the composite.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The applicability of imaging ToF SIMS to the characterisation of composite fracture surfaces has been clearly demonstrated. Not only are the locations of the fibre and resin components resolved, but the presence of potentially detrimental contaminants on the fibres within the fracture surfaces was also detectable. A direct correlation between the emission of fibre specific ions from the fracture surface, and the interfacial properties of the composite, can be made. For silanised glass fibres in an epoxy resin matrix it has proved possible to examine the uniformity of the silane deposit and the matrix on the protruding fibres and to readily differentiate between bare glass

Figure 8: CH⁺ (red)/O⁻ (green) overlay for a polished cross-section of a silanised glass fibre epoxy resin fracture surface.

surfaces. The presence of an interphase is clearly indicated by the sputtering of silane specific ions in the matrix adjacent to the fibres.

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REFERENCES

1. Denison, P., Jones, F.R., Brown, A., Humphrey, P. and Harvey, J., *J Mat Sci*, **23**, (1988), 2153.
2. Denison, P. and Jones, F.R., in 'Interfacial Phenomena in Composite Materials '91', Ed I Verpoest and F R Jones, Butterworth Heinemann Ltd, Oxford, (1991), p 129.
3. Wang, D., Jones, F.R. and Denison, P., *J Mat Sci*, **27**, (1992), 36.
4. Wang, D. and Jones, F.R., *Surface and Interface Anal*, (1993), in press.
5. Denison, P., Jones, F.R. and Watts, J.F., *Surface and Interface Anal*, **12**, (1988), 455.
6. Wang, D. and Jones, F.R., *Composites Sci and Tech*, (1993), in press.
7. Thomason, J.L., in *Interfacial Phenomena in Composite Materials*, '89, Ed F.R. Jones, Butterworths, Guildford, (1989), pp 171-180.